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DRS USER'S GUIDE

by

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Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison
Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory, Livermore, CA, USA

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Abstract

Three-dimensional climate models generate a large volume of time history data in the form of multidimensional arrays. Repeated postprocessing of these data is required to produce the relevant statistics needed for comparison with other model histories and observational data. Networks and desktop graphics workstations have made it possible to use remote supercomputers to perform climate simulations and postprocess their time history data, subsequently using local workstations to analyze, compare, and view the results. New software tools and methods are required to take advantage of these technological advances.

In climate research, it is common to extract two-dimensional, horizontal grids from datasets for analysis and display. In addition, it has become increasingly common to extract and visualize other two-dimensional cross-sections, as well as three- and four-dimensional fields, from large datasets. The ability to quickly animate images of such data is providing a new perspective for understanding climate models.

This document describes the Data Retrieval and Storage (DRS) software library, Version 2.11, which defines a data format and access methods, suitable for the data generated and used in climate model research. It is oriented toward use with models generating very large datasets on supercomputers, as well as with graphics workstations used for analysis and display of smaller subsets of data. This software is used extensively by the Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison (PCMDI) at Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory (LLNL) for the storage, postprocessing, analysis, and display of atmospheric model and observational data, and is freely available to collaborators in the climate modeling and diagnostic communities.

1. Introduction

The Data Retrieval and Storage (DRS) library of software was designed to serve as a data interface for use in development of general utility software to support climate modelling research. It accommodates the storage of gridded data from climate models and observed climate data. It is being used to provide the data input and output functions for post-processing and analysis applications and for random selection and retrieval of variables in interactive visualization applications at the Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Inter-comparison at the Lawrence Livermore National Laboratory.

The data form produced by the DRS library consists of a dictionary file, which describes the variables, and a separate data file, linked by identical names with fixed suffixes (.dic and .dat). Both files are randomly accessible. The DRS data form provides for a fairly thorough description of variables and their dimensions which helps to avoid error in the selection of variables and aids in the task of manipulating and sub-setting dimensions. This information is also very useful for identifying variables as they're displayed.

Each variable is described with four text strings. Only the minimal number of text strings, that will unambiguously determine a variable, need be given for a retrieval request. The dimensions of variables are defined in terms of two text strings and either a range and number of values or a description of a vector of monotonic values, which is stored as a separate variable. Dimensions need not be specified for a retrieval request unless a subset, a transpose, or a reversal of dimension direction is needed. A retrieval function is available to request data with a dimension wrapped around; it is frequently needed for longitude.

Descriptive information is passed, using a set function for naming the variable and another for defining it's dimensions. This information is kept in an internal variable descriptor block (VDB) for use in storing or retrieving the data. After storing data, this internal VDB retains it's description, perhaps with dimensions transposed (see Section 1.2 Data Storage below). After retrieving data, this internal VDB completely describes the data that was retrieved. Functions are available to get the information from this VDB.

The information in the internal VDB is either stored, or used to update a previously stored VDB, as data is stored. The information in the VDB may either be retained and modified for reuse in subsequent storing or retrieving of other variables, or it may be cleared.

1.1

Variable Descriptor Block (VDB)

The descriptive information for variables is stored in one random-access file, referred to as a dictionary and the data in another. The dictionary consists of VDBs, each of which describes a variable and its dimensions and includes a pointer, in bytes, to the location, within the data file, of the first value of the variable and, for each dimension, it includes a single positive increment, in bytes, between the locations of elements of the variable for adjacent values of that dimension. The data is stored such that the increment between elements of a variable in the first dimension is the smallest, as in FORTRAN.

There are four, fixed length, text string descriptors, referred to as naming strings, for each variable: (1) the data source for the variable - 120 bytes, (2) a short name for the variable - 16 bytes, (3) a descriptive title for the variable - 80 bytes, and (4) the units of the variable - 40 bytes. No two variables with identical text (printing characters only) in these four naming strings may be stored in a file. The retrieval process requires only the least number of these strings that will unambiguously determine the variable. The datatype of a variable may be either real ("R*4" or "R*8"), integer ("I*2" or "I*4" or "I*8"), or character ("C*n").

The dimensions of a variable may be either equally spaced or unequally spaced. Equally spaced dimensions are described with text strings for dimension name and dimension units, real values for first and last values of the dimension, and integer number of values. Unequally spaced dimensions must have been stored previously as *dimension variables*: one-dimensional, floating-point, monotonic variables. The description of an unequally spaced dimension is comprised of all four variable naming strings, the indices pointing to the first and last values, and the number of values. The dimension description includes an indicator to define whether it is equally or un-

equally spaced. No two dimension names may be the same for a variable.

Descriptive information is set into an internal VDB for use in storing or retrieving a variable. A get function will retrieve the requested data and a put function will store the data. After successful storage or retrieval the VDB will contain a complete and accurate description for the data that was stored or retrieved. Inquiry functions are provided for retrieving descriptive information without accessing the data file.

The internal VDB is altered by set, get, put, and clearing functions. Set functions alter only those arguments provided. Get and put functions reset the VDB with a description of the variable retrieved or stored.

1.2

Data Storage

Each block of data written is appended sequentially and contiguously to the end of the data file. As data is stored, the dictionary is updated, either by adding an entry for a new variable, or by altering the dimension description of an existing variable as data is appended.

Data is stored by first invoking set functions to place descriptive information into a VDB and then a put function to place the data into the file. During the put operation the naming strings in the current VDB are compared to those of variables previously stored in the file to determine whether a new variable is being defined (at least one naming string does not match) or not.

Each variable must have at least one dimension with positive length. Each dimension name must differ from all others for the variable. Single valued dimensions will be trivially transposed, if necessary, to the end of the set of dimensions, for example: $T(t=0,lon,lat,level)$ becomes $T(lon,lat,level,t=0)$.

If the naming strings match those of an existing variable, then the dimension names must also match (order of dimensions may differ) and the dimension values must either match existing values or be a monotonic extension to one of the last two dimensions. Extension of the last dimension and incremental fill of the next-to-last dimension

of a set of variables is possible if they're stored repetitively in the same sequence. For example, it is permissible to store:

p(i) = {1000,800,400}	then
lat(i)={89.14,...,-89.14}	then
Q(lon,lat,p=1000,t=0)	then
T(lon,lat,p=1000,t=0)	then
Q(lon,lat,p=800,t=0)	then
T(lon,lat,p=800,t=0)	then
Q(lon,lat,p=400,t=0)	then
T(lon,lat,p=400,t=0)	then
Q(lon,lat,p=1000,t=1)	then
T(lon,lat,p=1000,t=1)	then
Q(lon,lat,p=800,t=1)	then
T(lon,lat,p=800,t=1)	then
Q(lon,lat,p=400,t=1)	then
T(lon,lat,p=400,t=1)	then
X(lon,lat,t=1)	then
X(lon,lat,t=2)	

and they will be defined in the dictionary as:

```
p(i) = {1000,800,400},  
lat(i)={89.14,...,-89.14},  
Q(lon,lat={89.14,...,-89.14},p={1000,800,400},t={0,1}),  
T(lon,lat={89.14,...,-89.14},p={1000,800,400},t={0,1}),  
X(lon,lat={89.14,...,-89.14},t={1,2}).
```

The sequence for Q and T cannot be continued, because the increments between locations of the values of the variables in their p and t dimensions would not be a constant. The t dimension of X could be extended following this sequence.

Unequally spaced dimensions such as lat and p in the example above, must be stored as variables prior to their use. A function is provided for this purpose. Note that, in the previous example, it is not necessary to store t and lon as variables because they are equally spaced.

After storage of data, the VDB will retain the information actually used to store the data until it is either overwritten or cleared.

The DRS library supports random access to multidimensional sub-arrays of variables in a DRS file. The philosophy of the programming interface is to divorce the representation and ordering of data in the program from its representation and ordering in the file. The user specifies which data should be read, and how the data should appear in the program. The DRS library determines the mapping to the file representation and order, and handles the mapping on data retrieval. This implies the following functionalities:

- *subsetting*: The programmer specifies a range of values for each dimension of the variable to be retrieved.
- *coordinate <--> array index mapping*: The programmer specifies a range of a dimension using coordinate values, which are mapped internally to the proper array indices. Alternatively, user-level functions are provided to perform this mapping and to inquire file dimension lengths.
- *reordering of data on input*: If a coordinate range of a dimension is specified in an order that is the reverse of the file ordering, the data are reordered on input to reflect this reversal. Similarly if the dimensions themselves are transposed, the data are reordered.
- *data reformatting*: Data are transparently reformatted as necessary to the appropriate native mode floating-point or integer format.

An inquiry function is available for retrieving VDBs from a dictionary to the internal VDB, in sequence. It may also be used for retrieving all VDBs that have a particular naming string or set of naming strings. After retrieving a VDB it is then possible to get the information for display, perhaps for interactive selection of a variable, or to merely use the information to retrieve the variable, or to modify the information with set functions, if necessary, and store another variable.

The DRS library software is written in FORTRAN 77 and C. It currently runs on Sun, SGI, and HP9000 workstations and Cray/Unicos systems. The IEEE standards for floating point and integer values

and the ANSI standard ASCII character set are used for the dictionary information and, by default, for the data.

1.6

Error Handling

Each DRS function returns an integer error indication. Control is always returned to the calling program. By default, error messages are issued to the standard error output stream; the user can specify an alternate logical output unit for error logging. Additionally, the level of error reporting may be set to suppress warnings, or all error reports.

2. Using DRS

2.1

General Pattern of Usage

The DRS library consists of integer-valued functions that return a zero value on success and a non-zero value on failure. Files are available for inclusion in user applications that provide symbolic name assignments for values that are needed for function arguments and for testing error returns; for FORTRAN include 'drsdef.h' and for C include 'drscdf.h' files.

The general pattern of usage for DRS functions is:

1. Create or open a DRS dictionary and data file, for read or append, with `aslun`.
2. Clear the VDB with `cluvdb`.
3. Use `setname` to specify the variable. Only a minimal amount of naming information is required for retrieval.
4. When writing data with `getdat` define each equally spaced dimension with `setdim`, and define each unequally spaced dimension with `setvdim`.
5. When retrieving data with `getdat` use either `setdim` or `setvdim` to specify the dimensions. It is only necessary to specify a dimension if it is to be subsetted, reversed (in direction), or transposed. Only the name is needed for a transpose. If a dimension is not specified then the entire dimension is retrieved in the order it is stored.
6. When reading data with `getslab`, define vectors that specify: the order of dimensions, the first and last elements of each dimension range, the wrap-around cycles, and the number of values in each dimension. These are required as arguments.
7. When reading data use `getdat` or `getslab`.
8. When writing or incrementally extending a dimension of a variable use `putdat`.
9. To inquire the description of a variable use `inqdict`. The dimension information need not be specified, however if it is, then the

returned descriptors will describe the dimensions as they would have been retrieved with `getdat`.

10. After the data are retrieved or inquired, use `getname`, `getedim`, and/or `getcdim` to get information from the VDB on the data just retrieved or inquired.
11. Repeat the necessary Steps between 2 and 10, as necessary.
12. Close the files with `cllun`.

2.2

Variable Description Block

The Variable Description Block (VDB) is an internal 'scratchpad' that is used to pass descriptive information for a variable and its dimensions between the application and DRS. There is only one VDB; at any given time it may contain either user supplied descriptive information for a variable that will be read or written, or DRS supplied descriptive information for the variable that has just been read or written or inquired. When data is retrieved, only minimal information is necessary to describe the request but, after retrieval, the VDB totally describes the variable and the dimensions of the data that was actually retrieved.

The VDB contains the following fields for each variable:

- number of dimensions
- source comment field
- name of the variable
- title of the variable
- units identifier for the variable
- datatype: 'R*4' | 'R*8' | 'I*4' | 'I*8' | 'C*n'
- date and time that the variable was first written

The VDB also contains the following fields for each dimension of the variable:

- first and last element of the dimension, or a requested range
- number of elements in the dimension
- name of the dimension
- source comments, for unequally-spaced dimensions
- title of the dimension, for unequally-spaced dimensions
- units of the dimension
- vector of dimension values, for unequally-spaced dimensions

A number of DRS functions are provided for accessing the VDB. In general, the setxxx functions allow VDB fields to be set, and getxxx functions retrieve information from the VDB. Data are written with putdat and read with getdat and getslab functions and the VDB is modified to describe the variable just accessed. The inqdict function is used to retrieve information from the dictionary into the VDB without reading the data file. Finally the cluvdb function initializes the VDB. These functions are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1: VDB access functions

Function name	Description
cluvdb	Clear the VDB.
getname	Get the variable naming information and type.
getcdim	Get dimension information, including the vector of dimension values. The dimension may be equally or unequally spaced.
getedim	Get dimension information, including the dimension length, first and last values, but NOT including the actual vector of values.
getrge2	Map a dimension range to an index range.
getelemd	Get the variable type, as it exists in the file.
getnd	Get the number of dimensions of the variable.
inqdict	Search for a variable, and set up the VDB for subsequent getxxx functions.
setdate	Set the variable timestamp. The default is the current system date and time.
setdim	When writing data, declare a dimension as equally spaced, and set the dimension description. When reading data, set the dimension range and order of data to be retrieved.
setname	Set the name strings and datatype of a variable.
setrep	Set the file representation of a variable.
setvdim	When writing data, declare a dimension as unequally spaced, and set the dimension description. When reading data, set the dimension range and order of data to be retrieved.

It isn't always desirable, to specify a function argument, and for those instances, null arguments have been defined for strings, integers, and floating point values. A null character string is a single blank character (' '). A null integer is zero. A null floating-point argument is 1.0e20. When a null argument is supplied for setting an element of the VDB, that element is not changed. The function, `cluvdb` sets all VDB values to null. The functions that recognize null are listed in Table 2.

Table 2: Function arguments which may be null.

Function name	Argument	Null value	Interpretation
<code>aslun</code>	<code>datfil</code>	single blank	Same as dictionary name, with '.dat' extension.
<code>getslab</code> (retrieval only)	<code>fe, le</code>	1.0e20	On retrieval, if both values are null for a given dimension, set range to the entire dimension.
<code>setdim</code> (retrieval only)	<code>dun</code>	single blank	On retrieval, match any string on lookup.
	<code>idim</code>	0	On retrieval, use the value in the file.
	<code>df, dl</code>	1.0e20	On retrieval, if both values are null, set range to entire dimension.
<code>setname</code> (retrieval only)	<code>source, title, units</code>	single blank	On retrieval, match any string on lookup. On inquiry, if all strings (including name) are null, all variables are matched.
<code>setvdim</code> (retrieval only)	<code>dso, dti, dun</code>	single blank	On retrieval, match any string on lookup.
	<code>df, dl</code>	1.0e20	On retrieval, if both values are null, set range to entire dimension.

DRS files are opened, for read or append, with the `aslun` function. The `istat` argument is: `IDRS_CREATE` to create new DRS dictionary and data files, `IDRS_READ` to open read-only or `IDRS_EXTEND` to open for reading and/or appending.

DRS does not allow overwriting existing data.

DRS files should be closed with `cllun`, to ensure that the files are truncated to the proper length.

2.4.1 Example: Create a DRS File

Create a DRS file with dictionary filename 'drs.dic' and data filename 'drs.dat'. Assign Fortran logical units 7 and 8 to the dictionary and data files, respectively. Specifying a blank character for the data file name causes the file name to be generated from the dictionary file name, substituting a '.dat' extension.

```
include 'drsdef.h'
...
ierr = aslun(7, 'drs.dic', 8, ' ', IDRS_CREATE)
```

Data are written to DRS as follows:

1. If the variable has an unequally spaced dimension and the dimension variable has not yet been written, write it with `putvdim`. This may be done once for all values of the dimension, before writing any variables that use this dimension, or it may be written incrementally within a program loop.
2. Clear the VDB with `cluvdb`. All VDB values are set to null (see section 2.3).
3. Specify the variable with `setname`. If the variable is being written for the first time, then all naming information must be set. If the variable is being extended, then it is sufficient to specify only

those fields that are required to uniquely identify the variable, typically *name*.

4. Specify the dimension. If the dimension is equally spaced, use `setdim`, otherwise use `setvdim`.
5. Write the data with `putdat`.

2.5.1 Example: Write a 2-D Variable

The variable 'slp' is defined on an equally spaced 72 × 46 grid, representing longitude values from -180.0 to 175.0 degrees, inclusive, and latitude values of -90.0 to 90.0 degrees, inclusive. Write to the dictionary file with logical unit number 'lu'. The null argument in `setname` indicates that the data are in the default floating-point format. This is equivalent to specifying 'R*8' on the Cray or 'R*4' otherwise.

```
ierr = cluvdb()
ierr = setname('cgm83az coupled ocean-atmosphere',
              'slp', 'sea-level pressure', 'mb', ' ')
ierr = setdim(1, 'longitude', 'degrees', 72, -180.0,
              175.0)
ierr =
      setdim(2, 'latitude', 'degrees', 46, -90.0, 90.0)
ierr = putdat(lu, slp)
```

2.5.2 Example: Write a 3-D Variable with an Unequally Spaced Dimension

The variable 'slp' is defined on a 72 × 46 grid, at times 0.0 to 99.0, inclusive. The second dimension, latitude, is defined by the array 'gausslat'. Write the array 'slp', dimensioned as 72 × 46 × 100, to the data file whose related dictionary logical unit number is 'lu'.

```
ierr = cluvdb()
ierr = setname(' ', 'latitude', 'Gaussian latitudes',
              'degrees', ' ')
ierr = putvdim(lu, 46, gausslat, ig1, ig2)
...
ierr = cluvdb()
ierr = setname('cgm83az coupled ocean-atmosphere',
              'slp', 'sea-level pressure', 'mb', 'R*4')
ierr = setdim(1, 'longitude', 'degrees', 72, -180.0,
              175.0)
ierr = setvdim(2, ' ', 'latitude', ' ', ' ',
              gausslat(1),
```

```

    gausslat(46)
    ierr = setdim(3,'time','months',100, 0.0, 99.0)
    ierr = putdat(lu,slp)

```

2.5.3 Example: Incrementally Write a 3-D Variable

The variable 'slp' is defined on a 72 × 46 grid, at longitudes -180.0 to 175.0, latitudes -90.0 to 90.0, at times that are unequally spaced. The variable 'time' defines the current time. Write the variable 'slp' at each timestep.

```

do i=1,ntimes
    ...
    ierr = cluvdb()
    ierr = setname(' ','time','simulation time',
        'months','R*4')
    ierr = putvdim(lu,1,time,it1,it2)
    ...
    ierr = cluvdb()
    ierr = setname('cgm83az coupled ocean-atmosphere',
        'slp', 'sea-level pressure', 'mb',' ')
    ierr = setdim(1,'longitude','degrees',72,-180.0,
        175.0)
    ierr =
        setdim(2,'latitude','degrees',46,-90.0,90.0)
    ierr = setvdim(3,' ','time',' ',' ',time,time)
    ierr = putdat(lu,slp)
    ...
    (write some other variables for this timestep)
    ...
    (update time)

enddo

```

2.5.4 A Note on Extending Variables

DRS supports writing the data for a variable in increments, with one important restriction: the spacing between the data file locations for successive elements of a dimension must remain constant. This restriction is met even when iteratively writing data in increments for multiple variables if, within an iteration, the same amount of data is written. An error is returned from putdat if this restriction is not met.

For example, suppose that variable X is dimensioned 4 × 5 × 3, and the first increment written is the 20 values corresponding to the first value of dimension 3, followed by 100 bytes of data for other vari-

ables. If variable X is then extended by writing the 20 values corresponding to the second value of dimension 3, then 100 more bytes must be written before DRS will allow the final 20 values of X to be written. This is because the file spacing between successive elements in the third dimension must be constant.

DRS always writes new data immediately following the most recent data written. DRS does not allow existing data to be overwritten.

2.6

Reading Data

DRS data files are read as follows:

1. Clear the VDB with `cluvdb`.
2. Specify the variable being read with `setname`. It is sufficient to set only those naming strings necessary to uniquely identify the variable, specifying nulls (single blanks) for the other fields.

3A. If data is to be read without wrap-around (e.g., in a longitude dimension):

1. Specify the range of each dimension of the data with `setdim`, unless the entire dimension range is to be retrieved, and no transpose or reversal of the dimension is desired. In particular, if all data for a variable is to be retrieved as it exists in the file, then this step may be skipped entirely (see "Example: Read a 2-D Variable" on page 17).

2. Retrieve the data with `getdat`.

Note: The order in which the dimensions are specified defines the order of the dimensions of the data as it will be returned to the user. If this does not match the order of the data in the file, the data will be reordered on retrieval. Similarly, for a given dimension, the requested direction of the dimension (increasing or decreasing) may differ from that of the file.

3B. Otherwise, if data is to be read with wrap-around, retrieve the data with `getslab`. The order of the dimensions is specified by the `order` argument. This order must be inquired if not known in ad-

vance. The length of the wrap-around is specified for each dimension in the `cycle` argument. The dimension ranges are specified by the `fe` and `le` arguments.

2.6.1 `getdat` vs. `getslab`

The `getslab` function supports retrieval of data with one or more dimensions wrapped-around. This is useful if a dimension is circular (e.g., longitude) and the data are to be retrieved for a subrange that spans the 'break point' of the dimension. For example, if the variable is stored for a range of -180 to 175, `getslab` can retrieve the data for the range 0 to 360 inclusive, properly handling the duplication of data.

The function, `getdat`, may be simpler to use for development of general software if wrap-around is not needed. Table 3 summarizes the differences.

Table 3: `getdat` vs. `getslab`

<code>getdat</code>	<code>getslab</code>
Uses <code>setdim</code> to set dimension ranges in the VDB.	Sets dimension ranges in arrays to be used arguments.
Requires no dimension set up if data is to be retrieved as stored.	Requires set up of array arguments for ranges, order, cycle, and dimension sizes.
Is somewhat faster, and requires less memory.	Allocates an extra buffer and moves data twice.
Order of dimensions is specified by dimension name.	If a specific order of dimensions is required the inquiry function and string comparisons are necessary to determine the dimension order and set up the order array.
Supports dimension transposition, reversal, and subsetting.	Supports dimension transposition, reversal, subsetting, and wraparound.

2.6.2 Example: Read a 2-D Variable

Read the variable 'slp' described in section 2.5.1 on page 13.

```
include 'drsdef.h'
...
ierr = cluvdb()
ierr = setname(' ','slp',' ',' ',' ')
ierr = getdat(lu,slp,IDRS_BYTES_PER_WORD*72*46)
```

2.6.3 Example: Read a 2-D subset of a 3-D variable, using getdat

Assume 'slp' is the 72 × 46 × 100 array defined in section 2.5.2 on page 13. Read the 72 × 10 × 1 subarray of slp corresponding to the longitude range -180.0 to 175.0, latitude range -9.0 to +9.0, time = 30.0.

```
include 'drsdef.h'
...
ierr = cluvdb()
ierr = setname(' ','slp',' ',' ',' ')
ierr = setdim(1,'longitude',' ',72,-180.0,175.0)
ierr = setdim(2,'latitude',' ',10,-9.0,9.0)
ierr = setdim(3,'time',' ',1,30.0,30.0)
ierr = getdat(lu,slp,IDRS_BYTES_PER_WORD*72*10)
```

Note:

- Only the name parameter to setname is specified, as this is sufficient to uniquely define the variable. The remaining single blank characters are treated as null arguments.
- It is not strictly necessary in this example to call setdim for dimension 1, as the entire longitude dimension is to be retrieved in file order.
- The length of the dimension, as specified in the idim argument of setdim, indicates the maximum number of values in the dimension subrange to be retrieved.
- If the variable was written as in section 2.5.2 on page 13, the dimension order in the file would be <longitude, latitude, time>, with longitude varying most rapidly. For this example then, no reordering of data takes place. On the other hand, if the file ordering were different, the data would be reordered to <longitude, latitude, time>, as this is the order specified by the setdim calls.
- Although time is unequally-spaced, it is legitimate to specify the range with setdim.

2.6.4 Example: Read an Arbitrary Rectangular Region with Wraparound, using getslab

'c' is a 3-D variable, dimensioned 12 \times 15 \times 18. The first and third dimensions will be treated as 'wraparound' dimensions, since cycle(1) and cycle(3) are non-zero. It is known in advance that the result array will be 31 \times 2 \times 13, with the dimensions being transposed in the order 2,3,1.

```
include 'drsdef.h'
parameter (L1=31,L2=2,L3=13,R=3)
dimension cc(L1,L2,L3)
integer rank /R/
integer order(R) /2,3,1/
real fe(R) /-10.,13.,1./
real le(R) /20.,15.,25./
real cycle(R) /15.,0.0,24./
integer datadim(R)/L1,L2,L3/
integer setname,getslab,cluvdb
...
ierr=cluvdb()
ierr=setname(' ','c',' ',' ',' ')
ierr=getslab(lu,rank,order,fe,le,cycle,cc,datadim)
```

2.7

Inquiry

A variable may be inquired with inqdict, which sets the VDB to the first variable (or next variable) that has matching naming information. The function inqdict does not read any data.

The functions getname, getcdim, and getedim are used to retrieve dimension descriptors for the variable most recently read, written, or inquired. The function getname is used to get naming information about the variable. The function getcdim returns information about the dimensions of the variable, including the dimension vector. The function getedim returns the same data as getcdim, with the exception that the first and last dimension value, and the dimension length, are returned instead of the dimension vector. This is useful when the length of the dimension is not known in advance, or when it is known that the dimension is equally spaced.

2.7.1 Example: Inquire Variable Information

Get variable naming and dimension information for the first variable with name 'slp'.

```
include 'drsdef.h'
parameter( MXDVAR= ..., MXDIM=4)
real dvar(MXDVAR,MXDIM),dfe(MXDIM),dle(MXDIM)
character*120 source, dsource(MXDIM)
character*8 time, date, etype
character*16 name, dname(MXDIM)
character*40 units, dunits(MXDIM)
character*80 title, dtitle(MXDIM)
integer dtype(MXDIM)
integer cluvdb, setname, getdat, getname, getcdim
logical drstest
...
ierr = cluvdb()
ierr = setname(' ','slp',' ',' ',' ')
ierr = inqdict(lu,IDRS_GETFIRSTVAR)
ierr = getname(source, name, title, units, date,
  time, etype, ndim)
do idim=1,ndim
  if(drstest(getcdim(idim,dsource(idim),
    dname(idim),
    dtitle(idim), dunits(idim), dtype(idim), MXDVAR,
    dvar(1,idim), iretlen)))
    ... handle error ...
enddo
```

2.8

Error Handling

DRS functions return an integer error code. (An exception is the function `drstest`, which returns a logical value.) DRS has four levels of error reporting: `IDRS_NOREPORT`, `IDRS_WARNING`, `IDRS_FATAL`, and `IDRS_INTERNAL`. The default report level is `IDRS_WARNING`, which means that all DRS warning and fatal errors are reported. Errors are by default written to the Unix standard error output stream. The report level and error logical unit number can be set via `seterr`. Function `drstest` tests for fatal errors. DRS errors are listed on page 49.

Error values are defined in the include file 'drsdef.h' (Fortran) and 'drscdf.h' (C).

DRS keeps track of both the program and file data representations for each variable. The program representation is declared via the *typed* argument in *setname*. The file representation is optionally declared via the *setrep* function, and is retrieved via the *typed* argument of *getname*. By default, DRS stores floating-point data in IEEE 32-bit format, and integers are stored in 32-bit, 2's complement format. These are the Sun standard representations.

When data are written or read on Cray computers, DRS automatically translates the data to the default formats. The file representation for a particular variable may be explicitly set by calling *setrep* prior to writing the variable. For example, a program running on the Cray may set the file representation of a floating-point variable to 'IDRS_CRAY_R8'. DRS will then write the floating-point data without conversion. If this variable is subsequently read on the Suns, the conversion from Cray 64-bit to IEEE 32-bit format will be performed automatically.

IDRS_DICTREADERROR Error reading dictionary entries.
 IDRS_CANNOTREADDATA Error reading first block of data after open.

3.2 c11un: Close a DRS Dictionary and Data File

Fortran Interface integer function **c11un**(lu)

C Interface int **C11un**(int lu)

Arguments

lu Fortran logical unit number of the DRS dictionary file. The corresponding data file will also be closed. (Input, Integer)

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS Successful.

Comments

- On Cray computers, c11un must be called to ensure that the data and dictionary files are properly truncated.

3.3 inqlun: Inquire a DRS File

Fortran Interface integer function **inqlun**(lu, datafile, nvar, version)

C Interface int **Inqlun**(int lu, DRS_FILENAME datafile, int *nvar, float *version)

Arguments

lu Fortran logical unit number of the DRS dictionary file. (Input, Integer)

datafile File name of data file associated with the specified logical unit. (Output, CHARACTER*1024 on Unix, CHARACTER*248 on Cray)

nvar Number of variables in the DRS file. (Output, Integer)

version Version number of the dictionary file format. (Output, Real)

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS Successful.

IDRS_BADLUN No dictionary file with logical unit lu.

3.4 inqdict: Inquire Variables Similar to VDB

Fortran Interface integer function **inqdict**(lu, oper)

C Interface

```
int Inqdict(int lu, int oper)
```

Arguments

lu

Fortran logical unit number of the dictionary file. (Input, Integer)

oper

Flag indicating operation to perform: either IDRS_GETFIRSTVAR to set the VDB for the first variable that matches the naming information specified in the most recent setname call, or IDRS_GETNEXTVAR to get the next variable. These values are defined in 'drsdef.h' and 'drscdf.h'. (Input, Integer)

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS

Successful.

IDRS_BADLUN

No file with logical unit lu.

IDRS_NOMOREVARS

No more matching variables in dictionary.

IDRS_DICTREADERROR

Error reading dictionary file.

IDRS_NODICTFILE

Cannot find dictionary file.

Comments

- The dictionary file must have been opened with `withaslun`.
- This function should first be called with `IDRS_GETFIRSTVAR`, then subsequently with `IDRS_GETNEXTVAR`. After each successful return, the VDB contains all information on the variable, which can be retrieved with `getname`, `getedim`, and `getcdim`.
- When `inqdict` is called with `IDRS_GETFIRSTVAR`, the function copies the naming information specified via `setname` from the VDB to internal variables, which are saved between function invocations. This allows the VDB to be reset to the actual retrieved values, and also allows other functions affecting the VDB to be called. When called with `IDRS_GETNEXTVAR`, it is these internal variables, rather than the VDB, that determine the search. When no more variables are found, `inqdict` returns a value of `IDRS_NOMOREVARS`.
- Use `setname` to set the naming information.
- If `cluvdb` is called immediately before this function, or the naming information set via `setname` is blank, then on successive calls to `inqdict` all variables will be returned, with return value `IDRS_SUCCESS` (until no more variables are found. If the name is

nonblank, then the return value indicates whether a matching variable was found (IDRS_SUCCESS) or no more variables were found (IDRS_NOMOREVARS).

- If no more variables are found, the VDB naming information is set to null values (blanks).

3.5

prdict: Print Variable Metadata

Fortran Interface

integer function **prdict**(lup, lu)

C Interface

int **Prdict**(int lup, int lu)

Arguments

lup

Fortran logical unit number of print file. (Input, Integer)

lu

Fortran logical unit number of dictionary file. (Input, Integer)

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS

Successful.

IDRS_BADLUN

No file with logical unit lu.

IDRS_DICTREADERROR

Error reading dictionary file.

IDRS_NODICTFILE

Cannot find dictionary file.

Comments

- The dictionary file must have been opened with `haslun`.
- If `cluvdb` is called immediately before this function, information on all variables will be printed.
- Use `setname` to set the naming information.
- On return, the VDB naming information is set to null values (blanks).

4. Setting the VDB

4.1 cluvdb: Clear the VDB

Fortran Interface `integer function cluvdb()`

C Interface `int Cluvdb(void)`

Error returns
IDRS_SUCCESS

4.2 setdate: Set the Date and Time

Fortran Interface `integer function setdate(date, time)`

C Interface `int Setdate(DRS_DATE date, DRS_TIME time)`

Arguments

`date` Date that the data was generated. (Input, Character*8)

`time` Time that the data variable was generated. (Input, Character*8)

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS Successful.

Comments

- If `setdate` is not called for a variable, then DRS will automatically set the timestamp to the current date and time.

4.3 setdim: Set the VDB for an Equally Spaced Dimension

Fortran Interface `integer function setdim(n, dna, dun, idim, df, dl)`

C Interface `int Setdim(int n, DRS_NAME dna, DRS_UNITS dun, int idim, double df, double dl)`

Arguments

`n` Index of the dimension. (Input, Integer in the range 1 to 4)

`dna` Name of the dimension. (Input, Character*16)

`dun` Units of the dimension. (Input, Character*40)

`idim` Number of elements in the dimension. (Input, Integer)

`df` The first limit of the dimension range. (Input, Real)

d1	The last limit of the dimension range. (Input, Real)
Error returns	
IDRS_SUCCESS	Successful.
IDRS_BADDIM	n is not between 1 and 4, inclusive.
Comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The order of the dimensions cannot be changed once data has been stored for the variable. However, on retrieval, the dimensions can be transposed; that is, they can be specified in a different order than is stored in the data file. Similarly output data with transposed dimensions will be reordered to file ordering. • Only the data that exists between the dimension range limits will be retrieved. • On retrieval, the dimension name specified by the user must match a dimension stored in the file. Ifsetdim or setvdim is not called for a dimension on data retrieval, the dictionary file dimension specifications will be used. • On retrieval, set idim to 0, set df to 1.0e20, and set d1 to 1.0e20, to indicate that the entire dimension is to be used. This is useful if dimensions are to be transposed, but the whole dimension is to be retrieved. • On retrieval, the order of the data with respect to a given dimension will conform to the order specified bydf and d1, even if the dimension order in the file is reversed. For example, if the file order of a variable is such that latitude is decreasing, df = -90., and d1 = +90., then the data will be reordered on input such that the latitude is increasing. • For a given variable, dimension names must be unique. • Once a variable has been written, dimensions may not be added. • For a write, df and d1 values must be specified. For a read, if both values are set to null (1.0e20), the dictionary limits will be used. If only one value is set to null, it will be reset to the other value. • On retrieval, only the naming strings that uniquely identify the variable, typically 'name', need be specified.

- For a write, use `setdim` to specify an evenly-spaced dimension. Use `setvdim` to specify an unevely-spaced dimension. For retrieval, `setdim` and `setvdim` may be used interchangeably.

4.4 `setname`: Set the VDB Naming Information

Fortran Interface integer function **setname**(source, name, title, units, typed)

C Interface int **Setname**(DRS_SOURCE source, DRS_NAME name, DRS_TITLE title, DRS_UNITS units, DRS_TYPE typed)

Arguments

`source` Comments. (Input, Character*120)

`name` Short name of the variable. (Input, Character*16)

`title` Long name of the variable. (Input, Character*80)

`units` Units of the variable. (Input, Character*40)

`typed` Machine representation of the variable in memory. The format is '(element_type)*(element_byte_length)', where (element_type) is either {R (real), I (integer), or C (character)}, and (element_byte_length) is the number of bytes in each variable element. Examples: 'R*4', 'I*4', 'C*16'. The default value is 'R*4' on the Suns, 'R*8' on the Crays if `typed` is blank, or the file representation is floating-point, as set by `setrep`. The default value is 'I*4' on the Suns, 'I*8' on the Crays if the file representation is integer (Input, Character*8)

Error returns

`IDRS_SUCCESS` Successful.

Comments

- Call `setrep` to set the representation of the variable in the data file to a non-default type.

4.5 `setrep`: Set the Variable Element File Representation

Fortran Interface integer function **setrep**(rep)

C Interface int **Setrep**(int rep)

Arguments

rep

Machine representation code:

Table 4: Representation codes

Code	Meaning
IDRS_I4	2's complement, 4-byte integer (Sun integer)
IDRS_I8	2's complement, 8-byte integer (Cray integer)
IDRS_IEEE_R4	IEEE 32-bit floating point
IDRS_CRAY_R8	Cray 64-bit floating point
IDRS_ASCII	ASCII character string
IDRS_DEFAULT	Set to default, depending on element program representation: IDRS_IEEE_R4 for floating-point data, IDRS_I4 for integer data.

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS

Successful.

Comments

- Call `setname` to set the element program representation in argument (*typed*).

4.6

`setvdim`: Set the VDB for an Unequally Spaced Dimension

Fortran Interface

```
integer function setvdim(idim, dso, dna, dti, dun, df, dl)
```

C Interface

```
int setvdim(int idim, DRS_SOURCE dso, DRS_NAME dna, DRS_TITLE dti, DRS_UNITS dun, double df, double dl)
```

Arguments

idim

Index of the dimension. (Input, Integer in the range 1 to 4)

dso

Source description for the (unequally spaced) dimension. (Input, Character*120)

dna

Name of the dimension. (Input, Character*16)

dti

Title of the (unequally spaced) dimension. (Input, Character*80)

dun	Units of the dimension. (Input, Character*40)
df	The first value of the dimension range. (Input, Real)
d1	The last value of the dimension range. (Input, Real)
Error returns	
IDRS_SUCCESS	Successful.
IDRS_BADDIM	idim number not in the range 1 to 4.
Comments	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Naming information (dso, dna, dti, dun) must be unique with respect to other variables in the data file. • The portion of the dimension variable being referenced must have been written to the data file with putvdim prior to the putdat call. • When the data for a variable is initially output, the call to setvdim indicates that the dimension is unevenly-spaced. To specify an evenly-spaced dimension, use setdim. • The functions setdim and setvdim may be used interchangeably for retrieval.

5. Retrieving from the VDB

5.1 getname: Get the VDB Variable Information

Fortran Interface integer function **getname**(source, name, title, units, date, time, typed, nd)

C Interface int **Getname**(DRS_SOURCE source, DRS_NAME name, DRS_TITLE title, DRS_UNITS units, DRS_DATE date, DRS_TIME time, DRS_TYPE typed, int *nd)

Arguments

source Comments. (Output, Character*120)

name Short name of the variable. (Output, Character*16)

title Long name or description of the variable. (Output, Character*80)

units Units of the variable. (Output, Character*40)

date Date that the data were generated. (Output, Character*8)

time Time that the data variable was generated. (Output, Character*8)

typed Descriptor for the variable, with format '(element_type)*(element_byte_length)', where (element_type) is one of {R (real), I (integer), or C (character)} and (element_byte_length) is the number of bytes in each variable element. Example: 'R*4', 'I*4', 'C*16'. Default is 'R*4' on the Suns, 'R*8' on the Crays. Cray integers should be specified as 'I*8'. (Output, Character*8)

nd Number of dimensions of the variable. (Output, Integer in the range 1 to 4)

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS Successful.

5.2 getcddim: Get Dimension Variable

Fortran Interface integer function **getcddim**(idim, dso, dna, dti, dun, dtype, reqlen, var, retlen)

C Interface int **Getcddim**(int idim, DRS_SOURCE dso, DRS_NAME dna, DRS_TITLE dti, DRS_UNITS dun, int *dtype, int reqlen, float var[], int *retlen)

Arguments

<code>idim</code>	Index of the dimension. (Input, Integer in the range 1 to 4)
<code>dso</code>	Source of the dimension. (Output, Character*120)
<code>dna</code>	Name of the dimension. (Output, Character*16)
<code>dti</code>	Title of the dimension. (Output, Character*80)
<code>dun</code>	Units of the dimension. (Output, Character*40)
<code>dtype</code>	(Output, Integer, one of <code>IDRS_EQUALLY_SPACED</code> or <code>IDRS_UNEQUALLY_SPACED</code> , as defined in 'drsdef.h' and 'drscdf.h')
<code>reqlen</code>	Maximum number of words to return in <code>var</code> . (Input, Integer)
<code>var</code>	Returned dimension variable. (Output, array of Reals)
<code>retlen</code>	Number of words returned in <code>var</code> . (Output, Integer)
Error returns	
<code>IDRS_SUCCESS</code>	Successful.
<code>IDRS_DICTREADERROR</code>	Error reading dictionary file.
<code>IDRS_NODICTFILE</code>	No dictionary file found.
<code>IDRS_BADLEN</code>	The length of <code>var</code> , as specified by <code>reqlen</code> , is not large enough to hold the return data.

Comments

- This function works for both equally spaced and unequally spaced dimensions. If the dimension is equally spaced, the source and title are returned as blanks. If `getcdim` is called after data are retrieved with `getslab`, the dimension variable `var` will reflect any wraparound specified.
- If `reqlen = 0`, then all return parameters except `var` are set, and the function returns `IDRS_BADLEN`. Report of this error may be suppressed with `seterr`.
- If the length of the dimension vector is not known in advance, it may be obtained with `getedim`.
- If the dimension is equally spaced, then `dso` and `dti` are returned as blank.

5.3 `getedim`: Get the Non-Vector Dimension Information

Fortran Interface `integer function getedim(idim, dso, dna, dti, dun,`

`dtype, dlen, df, dl)`

C Interface

`int Getedim(int idim, DRS_SOURCE dso, DRS_NAME dna, DRS_TITLE dti, DRS_UNITS dun, int *dtype, int *dlen, float *df, float *dl)`

Arguments

<code>idim</code>	Index of the dimension. (Input, Integer in the range 1 to 4)
<code>dso</code>	Source of the dimension. (Output, Character*120)
<code>dna</code>	Name of the dimension. (Output, Character*16)
<code>dti</code>	Title of the dimension. (Output, Character*80)
<code>dun</code>	Units of the dimension. (Output, Character*40)
<code>dtype</code>	(Output, Integer, one of <code>IDRS_EQUALLY_SPACED</code> or <code>IDRS_UNEQUALLY_SPACED</code> , as defined in 'drsdef.h' and 'drscdf.h')
<code>dlen</code>	Number of elements in the dimension. (Output, Integer)
<code>df</code>	The first value of the dimension. (Output, Real)
<code>dl</code>	The last value of the dimension. (Output, Real)

Error returns

<code>IDRS_SUCCESS</code>	Successful.
<code>IDRS_BADDIM</code>	<code>idim</code> outside of range defined for this variable.

Comments

- If the dimension is equally spaced, then the source and title are returned as blank.

5.4

`getrge2`: Get Index Range

Fortran Interface

integer function **getrge2**(`lu, idim, df, dl, if, il, daf, dal`)

C Interface

`int Getrge2(int lu, int idim, double df, double dl, int *if, int *il, float *daf, float *dal)`

Arguments

<code>lu</code>	Dictionary file logical unit number (Input, Integer)
<code>idim</code>	Index of the dimension. (Input, Integer in the range 1 to 4)
<code>df</code>	First value of user range. (Input, Real)

<code>d1</code>	Last value of user range. (Input, Real)
<code>if</code>	Index corresponding to first user value. (Output, Integer)
<code>i1</code>	Index corresponding to last user value. (Output, Integer)
<code>daf</code>	Actual value in file, corresponding to <code>d1</code> . (Output, Real)
<code>da1</code>	Actual value in file, corresponding to <code>i1</code> (Output, Real)
Error returns	
<code>IDRS_SUCCESS</code>	Successful.
<code>IDRS_NORANGE</code>	The range [<code>elem1,elem2</code>] is outside the variable's range.

Comments

- The index range [`ind1,ind2`], and the user range [`dlow,dhigh`] correspond to the actual range of values that DRS will retrieve if `setdim` is called with the range [`elem1,elem2`]. Hence, this function provides a way to determine the actual number of values that will be retrieved by `getdat`, without actually reading any data. `elem1` and `elem2` need not correspond exactly to dimension values; the actual user range that DRS will retrieve is [`dlow,dhigh`].
- The dimension may be either equally spaced or unequally spaced.

5.5 `getelemnd`: Get Current Variable Element Description

Fortran Interface `integer function getelemnd(etype, bpe)`

C Interface `int Getelemnd(int *etype, int *bpe)`

Arguments

`etype` Element type, as it exists in the file. (Output, Integer: one of `IDRS_CRAY_R8`, `IDRS_IEEE_R4`, `IDRS_I8`, `IDRS_I4`, or `IDRS_ASCII`, as defined in `drsdef.h` and `drscdf.h`)

`bpe` Number of bytes per element, as the data exists in the file. (Output, Integer)

Error returns

`IDRS_SUCCESS` Successful.

`IDRS_BADTYPE` A bad element type was found.

Comments

- The VDB must have been set (i.e., via `getdat` or `inqdict`).

5.6

`getnd`: Get the Number of Dimensions

Fortran Interface
Arguments

integer function **getnd**(nd)

nd

Number of dimensions for the current variable, i.e., the variable rank. (Output, Integer in the range 1 to 4)

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS

Successful.

Comments

- This function provides a convenient alternative to `getname` when only the variable rank is needed. The VDB must have been set via a call to `getdat`, `putdat`, `getslab`, or `inqdict`.

6. Reading and Writing Data

6.1 putdat: Write or Extend a Data Variable

Fortran Interface integer function **putdat**(lu, var)

C Interface int **Putdat**(int lu, int var[])

Arguments

lu Fortran logical unit number of the DRS dictionary file. (Input, Integer)

var Data array. (Input, array of Reals, Integers, or Characters)

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS Successful.

IDRS_BADLU lu does not exist or cannot be written or read.

IDRS_BADTYPE Data length or data type illegal.

IDRS_BADDIM Input dimensions or dimension limits are incorrect.

IDRS_AMBIGUITYEXISTS An ambiguity exists between user and file specifications:
More than one variable is similar to the naming information
- OR -
the user-specified file representation does not match the actual file representation
- OR -
the user-specified dimension names are not similar to the actual dimension names.

IDRS_CANNOTADDDATA Data cannot add to existing data.

IDRS_DICTFULL Too many dictionary entries.

IDRS_BADDIMTYPE Dimension types disagree.

IDRS_NORANGE Requested range is outside the dimension range.

Comments

- After a variable write, the VDB reflects how the data were stored. For instance, in some circumstances, DRS may reorder the dimensions within the data file.

6.2 putvdim: Write or Extend a Dimension Variable

Fortran Interface integer function **putvdim**(lu, dlen, dvar, if, il)

C Interface int **Putvdim**(int lu, int len, float dvar[], int *if, int *il)

Arguments

lu Fortran logical unit number of the DRS. (Input, Integer in the range 1 to 99)

dlen Number of elements in the dimension. (Input, Integer)

dvar Values of the (unequally spaced) dimension elements. (Input, array of Reals)

if Index of the first element of the input dvar. (Output, Integer)

il Index of the last input element of the dvar. (Output, Integer)

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS Successful.

IDRS_NOTMONOTONE The dimension variable is not strictly monotone, or adding to an existing variable does not preserve strict monotonicity.

IDRS_BADLEN dlen is not a positive integer.

IDRS_DICTREADERROR Error reading dictionary file.

IDRS_NODICTFILE Could not find dictionary file.

IDRS_BADLU lu does not exist or cannot be written or read.

IDRS_BADDIM Input dimensions are incorrect.

IDRS_AMBIGUITYEXISTS An ambiguity exists between user and file specifications.

IDRS_CANNOTADDDATA Data cannot add to existing data.

IDRS_DICTFULL Too many dictionary entries.

Comments

- If the dimension variable is being extended (i.e., only a portion of the dimension variable is being written with the call), then the return indices reflect the position of the input dvar within the resulting (entire) dimension variable.
- After a write, the VDB reflects how the dimension data were stored.

- `dvar` must be an array of reals. The `typed` parameter of `setname` is ignored.
- On first writing the dimension variable, complete naming information should be set via `setname`. On subsequent writes, only enough information to unambiguously reference the variable need be specified.
- `putvdim` checks that, after the write, the resulting dimension variable will be strictly monotone.

6.3

getdat: Read a Data Variable

Fortran Interface

integer function **getdat**(lu, var, isize)

C Interface

int **Getdat**(int lu, int var[], int isize)

Arguments

lu

Fortran logical unit number of the DRS dictionary file, in the range 1 to 99. (Input, Integer)

var

Data variable values. (Output, array of Reals, Integers, or Characters)

isize

Length of `var` in bytes. (Input, Integer)

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS

Successful.

IDRS_BADLU

Bad logical unit number.

IDRS_VDBNOTFOUND

Specified variable is not in the dictionary

IDRS_DICTREADERROR

Error reading dictionary file.

IDRS_NODICTFILE

No dictionary file found.

IDRS_BADDIMNAME

Bad dimension name specified.

IDRS_CANNOTREADDATA

Cannot read data file.

IDRS_BADLEN

`isize` is less than the length of the data to be returned.

IDRS_BADDIMTYPE

A dimension type was specified with `setdim` but is unequally spaced, or was specified with `setvdim` but is equally spaced.

Comments

- `isize` should be set to a value at least as large as the amount of data to be returned, in bytes.
- Use `inqdict` to get information about a variable, without actually reading the data.
- `getdat` always fills contiguous elements of `var`, starting with the first element.

6.4 getslab: Read a 'slab' of Data

Fortran Interface	integer function getslab (lu, rank, order, fe, le, cycle, var, datadim)
C Interface	int Getslab (int lu, int rank, int order[], float fe[], float le[], float cycle[], void *var, int datadim[])
Arguments	
lu	Fortran logical unit number of the DRS dictionary file. (Input, Integer)
rank	Number of variable dimensions. (Input, Integer)
order	Array of dimension numbers. (Input, Array of Integers, of length rank)
fe	Array of first elements of the ranges to be retrieved, in the same order as <code>order</code> . (Input, Array of Reals, of length rank)
le	Array of last elements of the ranges to be retrieved, in the same order as <code>order</code> . (Input, Array of Reals, of length rank)
cycle	Array of dimension cycles (if the dimension wraps around), in the same order as <code>order</code> . Specify 0.0 if the dimension does not wrap-around. (Input, Array of Reals, of length rank)
var	Data variable values. (Output, array of Reals, Integers, or Characters)
datadim	Number of elements in each dimension of <code>var</code> , in the same order as <code>order</code> . (Input, Array of Integers, of length rank)
Error returns	
IDRS_SUCCESS	Successful.
IDRS_BADLU	Bad logical unit number.
IDRS_VDBNOTFOUND	Specified variable is not in the dictionary

IDRS_DICTREADERROR	Error reading dictionary file.
IDRS_NODICTFILE	No dictionary file found.
IDRS_CANNOTREADDATA	Cannot read data file.
IDRS_BADLEN	The dimensions of <code>var</code> , as specified by <code>datadim</code> , are not large enough for data to be returned.
IDRS_BADDIM	An element of <code>order</code> is not between 1 and 4, inclusive.
IDRS_NOMEMORY	Cannot allocate memory for internal read buffer.

Comments

- A *slab* of data is defined as a rectangular multidimensional section of the data variable defined by the user dimension ranges $[fe[i], le[i]]$, $i=0..rank-1$. If a user dimension range is larger than the variable dimension range and `wraparound` is specified ($cycle[i] > 0.0$), then the dimension is treated as circular, and the data are wrapped around, in that dimension. If `wraparound` is not specified ($cycle[i]=0.0$), then the action of `getslab` is identical to `getdat`, returning the data corresponding to the dimension subranges specified with `fe` and `le`.
- If no transposition of dimensions is desired, specify `orders=[1 2 ... rank]`; otherwise the i th dimension returned will be `order[i-1]`.
- The range $[fe[i], le[i]]$ may be larger than the actual range of dimension values (in the data file). If $cycle[i] \leq 0.0$, then the dimensions will be treated as circular, and the data will be read with `wraparound`.
- `setname` should be called before `getslab`. Calls to `setdim` and `setvdim` are ignored.
- Data are returned in Fortran order (first dimension varying most rapidly).
- Specify $cycle[i-1]=0.0$ if no `wraparound` is desired for the i th dimension. It is an error if $cycle[i] < 0.0$ or $cycle[i] \geq$ actual dimension range.

6.5 putdic: Modify an existing dictionary entry

Fortran Interface integer function **putdic**(**lu**,**iopt**)

C Interface int **Putdic**(int lu, int iopt)

Arguments

lu Fortran logical unit number of the DRS dictionary file. (Input, Integer)

iopt Write option, one of: IDRS_BLANKS_ARE_NULL (reset blank input strings to current values) or IDRS_BLANKS_ARE_LITERAL (treat blanks as literals), as defined in drsdef.h and drscdf.h.

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS Successful.

IDRS_BADLU Bad logical unit number.

IDRS_VDBNOTFOUND Specified variable is not in the dictionary

IDRS_DICTREADERROR Error reading dictionary file.

IDRS_NODICTFILE No dictionary file found.

IDRS_CANNOTWRITEDIC Cannot write to dictionary file.

IDRS_DUPLICATEVAR New naming strings would conflict with an existing variable.

IDRS_BADDIM The new name of a dimension variable conflicts with another dimension.

Comments

- `putdic` may be used to modify an existing dictionary entry, without reading or writing data. Under most circumstances it is not necessary to use this function. The dictionary file is created and updated, using the VDB information, as data is written. However, it may be necessary to modify a descriptor for a variable after the data has been written.
- The dictionary entries that can be modified by this function are: variable source, name, title, units, timestamp, and dimension name and units.
- The dictionary entries that cannot be modified are: variable type, dimension order, dimension lengths, and dimension values.

- Sample usage:

```
ierr=cluvdb()
ierr=setname(oldsr,oldnam,oldtitl,oldunits,cdum)
ierr=inqdict(lu,IDRS_GETFIRSTVAR)
ierr=setname(newsrc,newnam,newtitl,newunits)
ierr=setdate(newdate,newtime)
ierr=setdim(1,newdnam,newdun,idum,dum,dum)
ierr=setdim(2,...)
ierr=putdic(lu,IDRS_BLANKS_ARE_NULL)
```

- Names of dimension variables must be updated by directly modifying the (dimension) variable, not via setvdim. Changing the name of a dimension variable changes the name of the corresponding dimension for all variables with that dimension.
- It is only necessary to call setname and/or setdim for information that changes, since the default is to leave the names the same if `iopt = IDRS_BLANKS_ARE_NULL`. If `iopt = IDRS_BLANKS_ARE_LITERAL`, blank strings are treated literally as new values.

6.6

drsautosync: Set autosynchronization flag

Fortran Interface

```
integer function drsautosync(lu,iopt)
```

C Interface

```
int Drsautosync(int lu, int iopt)
```

Arguments

`lu`

Fortran logical unit number of the DRS dictionary file. (Input, Integer)

`iopt`

Synchronization option, one of: `IDRS_SYNC_ON` (synchronize dictionary and data file after each write, the default), or `IDRS_SYNC_OFF` (synchronize dictionary and data files only when `clun` or `drssync` are called).

Error returns

`IDRS_BADSYNCOPT`

Invalid synchronization option

Comments

- By default, DRS flushes output to dictionary and data files after each call to `putdat`. If data is typically written in many small chunks, performance may be improved on some platforms by setting a large buffer size when the DRS library is compiled, and/or

turning off autosynchronization. In this case, data is actually written only when the buffer fills, `drssync` is called, or `cllun` is called.

- If autosynchronization is turned off, it is important to call `cllun` to close the file. Otherwise, data may be lost.
- The buffer size is set statically when the library is created. To reset buffer size, set parameter `idatrecl` in `filedrscom.h`, before compiling the DRS library. `idatrecl` should be a multiple of 512 bytes.
- Autosynchronization may be turned on or off at any time after a file is opened, and may be called more than once for a given file.
- This function was added in Version 2.9.

6.7 `drssync`: Flush data

Fortran Interface `integer function drssync(lu)`

C Interface `int Drssync(int lu)`

Arguments

`lu` Fortran logical unit number of the DRS dictionary file. (Input, Integer)

Error returns

`IDRS_BADLU` Bad logical unit number.

`IDRS_CANNOTWRITEDATA` Cannot flush data.

Comments

- By default, DRS flushes data after each call to `putdat`, ensuring that the dictionary and data files are synchronized. It is only necessary to use `drssync` if autosynchronization has been turned off, via `drsautosync`.

7. Error Handling

7.1 seterr: Set Error Reporting Parameters

Fortran Interface integer function **seterr**(ierrlun, reportlevel)

C Interface int **Seterr**(int ierrlun, int reportlevel)

Arguments

ierrlun Fortran logical unit number for error output (defaults to the logical unit for standard error output, typically 0 or 6). (Input, Integer in the range 1 to 99)

reportlevel Minimum level of errors to report; defaults to IDRS_WARNING. (Input, Integer: either IDRS_NOREPORT (do not report errors), IDRS_FATAL (report only fatal errors), IDRS_WARNING (report warning and fatal errors), or IDRS_INTERNAL (report all nonsuccess returns; this is recommended only for debugging))

Error returns

IDRS_SUCCESS Successful.

IDRS_BADLU Invalid logical unit number.

Comments

- This function can be called as often as needed to fine-tune error reporting.

7.2 drstest: Test for a Fatal DRS Error

Fortran Interface Logical Function **drstest**(ierr)

C Interface int **Drstest**(int ierr)

Arguments

ierr DRS Error number. (Input, Integer)

Function returns

.true. If the DRS error is fatal.

.false. If the DRS error is nonfatal, or no error occurred.

8. Glossary

data file	The file, generated by DRS, that contains user data.
dictionary file	The file, generated by DRS, that contains descriptions of the variables in the data file, i.e., metadata. The dictionary file essentially contains a VDB for each variable in the data file.
dimension	<p>A strictly monotonic, real-valued vector that represents an independent variable. All dimensions have a name, dimension number, units, and type (equally spaced or vector representation). The name must be unique with respect to the other dimensions of the given variable. Dimensions can be equally spaced or unequally spaced (vector representation).</p> <p>An equally spaced dimension is a dimension for which the increment between successive values is a constant. Consequently, an equally spaced dimension can be represented by the triplet <length, first element, last element>.</p> <p>An unequally spaced or vector dimension is a dimension for which the increment between successive values may vary. An unequally spaced dimension is represented by a real-valued, one-dimensional, strictly monotonic vector of values. In contrast to equally spaced dimensions, DRS implements unequally spaced dimensions as variables in their own right. Like all variables, they are named by name, source, title, and units, which must be unique with respect to ALL variables in the dictionary. An unequally spaced dimension may be shared by different variables.</p>
dimension variable	A variable that is used as a dimension for another variable.
element	An individual value of a dimension or variable.
metadata	Data describing the variable, specifically, values in the VDB.
variable	A data array of up to four dimensions. More formally, a function that maps the cross-product of a set of dimensions into either the REALs, INTEGERS, or CHARACTER strings. A variable has four naming strings, which as a group uniquely define the variable: source, name, title, and units.
Variable Description	
Block (VDB)	The VDB is an internal data structure that is used to set or inquire about variable and dimension descriptions. The dictionary file

contains the equivalent of a VDB for each variable in the data file, including dimension variables.

9. Building Executables

DRS libraries and include files are currently available for Sun (SunOS 4.1.X and Solaris 2.X), Cray/Unicos, SGI/Irix, DEC Alpha/OSF, IBM RS6000/AIX and HP9000/HP-UX platforms. The files needed to compile and link an executable are:

- `libdrs.a` The DRS library
- `drsdef.h` Fortran include file
- `drscdf.h` C include file

9.1 Sample compile/link commands for Fortran source code

The following examples assume that the DRS library `libdrs.a` is contained in directory `drslib`:

Cray/Unicos	<code>cf77 -L <i>drslib</i> -l drs -l f testdrs.f -o testdrs</code>
DEC Alpha/OSF	<code>f77 testdrs.f -L<i>drslib</i> -ldrs -o testdrs</code>
HP 9000/HP-UX	<code>fort77 +U77 testdrs.f -L<i>drslib</i> -ldrs -lm -o testdrs</code>
IBM RS6000/AIX	<code>xlf testdrs.f -L<i>drslib</i> -ldrs -lm -o testdrs</code>
SGI/Irix	<code>f77 testdrs.f -L<i>drslib</i> -ldrs -o testdrs</code>
SunOS 4.1.X	<code>f77 testdrs.f -L<i>drslib</i> -ldrs -o testdrs</code>
Sun/Solaris 2.X	<code>f77 -o testdrs testdrs.f -L<i>drslib</i> -ldrs -lucb</code>

9.2 Sample compile/link commands for C source code

The following examples assume that the DRS library `libdrs.a` is contained in directory `drslib`, and the include file `drscdf.h` is contained in directory `drsinc`:

Cray/Unicos	<code>cc -I<i>drsinc</i> -L <i>drslib</i> -l drs -l f testdrs.c -o testdrs</code>
DEC Alpha/OSF	<code>cc -c -I<i>drsinc</i> -o testdrs.o testdrs.c</code> <code>f77 -nofor_main testdrs.o -L<i>drslib</i> -ldrs -o test2</code>
HP 9000/HP-UX	<code>cc -I<i>drsinc</i> testdrs.c -L<i>drslib</i> -ldrs -lU77 -lcl -lm -o testdrs</code>
IBM RS6000/AIX	<code>cc -I<i>drsinc</i> -c testdrs.c -o testdrs.o</code> <code>xlf testdrs.o -o testdrs -L<i>drslib</i> -ldrs -lm</code>
SGI/Irix	<code>cc -I<i>drsinc</i> testdrs.c -L<i>drslib</i> -ldrs -lF77 -lm -lU77 -lI77 \</code> <code>-lisam -lc -o testdrs</code>

SunOS 4.1.X	<code>cc -Idrsinc -o testdrs testdrs.c -Ldrslib -ldrs \</code> <code>-Bstatic -lF77 -Bdynamic</code>
Sun/Solaris 2.X	<code>cc -Idrsinc -o testdrs testdrs.c -Ldrslib -ldrs -lF77 -lm</code>

9.3 Availability (PCMDI)

This section describes the availability of installed DRS libraries and include files, at the Program for Climate Model Diagnosis and Intercomparison. The format of the entries is *machine:directory*, where *machine* is an Internet machine address, or CFS for the NERSC CFS mass-storage system. *directory* is the directory name(s) containing the DRS library `libdrs.a`, and include files `filesdrsdef.h` and `drscdf.h`. Directories beginning with `/afs` are AFS (Andrew File System) directories.

Cray/Unicos (Cray-2)	<code>CFS:/017374/drs/unicos/dev</code>
Cray/Unicos (C90)	<code>a.nersc.gov:/afs/nersc.gov/software/pub/drs/[lib,include]</code>
HP 9000/HP-UX	<code>sas-hp.nersc.gov:/afs/nersc.gov/software/pub/drs/[lib,include]</code>
SGI/Irix	<code>cloud.llnl.gov:/usr/local/drs/drslib</code>
SunOS 4.1.X	<code>/usr/local/PCMDI/[lib,include]</code>
Sun/Solaris 2.X	<code>/pcmdi/cirrus/drs_solaris</code> <code>sas-sun.nersc.gov:/afs/nersc.gov/software/pub/drs/[lib,inclu</code>

9.4 Public availability

The DRS library, utilities, and documentation are publicly available on the World Wide Web, and via anonymous ftp.

WWW access	<code>http://www-pcmdi.llnl.gov/drach/DRS.html</code>
anonymous ftp	<code>sprite.llnl.gov/pub/drs</code>

10. Conclusions

The DRS library and utilities are heavily used by the PCMDI program at LLNL for storing and accessing data used in climate model research. PCMDI is continuing to develop this software. Features which may be included in future releases include the ability to pack and unpack data, better support for non-uniform grids, and an improved capability to handle spectral representations of data. DRS is available to collaborators in the climate modeling and diagnostic communities on request. The authors welcome and encourage comments and inquiries.

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APPENDIX A: DRS Errors

DRS has four levels of errors: IDRS_SUCCESS (zero value), IDRS_WARNING (values between 1000 and 1999 inclusive), IDRS_FATAL (values between 1 and 999 inclusive), and IDRS_INTERNAL (values between 2000 and 2999 inclusive). The actual numeric values are listed here only for reference; there is no guarantee that they will not change in future releases. Consequently, error testing should compare against the named parameters rather than the numeric values.

DRS Errors are defined in the Fortran include file 'idrsdef.h' and the C include file 'drscdf.h'.

A.1 DRS Errors by Number

- 0 (IDRS_SUCCESS), The function completed successfully.
- 1: (IDRS_NOMEMORY), Cannot allocate dynamic memory.
- 2002: (IDRS_BINFAILED), Data value lookup failed.
- 3: (IDRS_BADLEN), vector length was .lt.1 or not large enough for actual data.
- 4: (IDRS_NOMONO), No monotonicity specified for a search vector of length greater than 1.
- 5: (IDRS_NOCOMPARISON), Variable names do not compare.
- 6: (IDRS_VDBNOTFOUND), Variable not found in dictionary.
- 7: (IDRS_BADDIM), An input dimension or dimension limit is incorrect.
- 8: (IDRS_NOTMONOTONE), Resulting dimension variable will not be monotone.
- 9: (IDRS_DICTREADERROR), Error reading dictionary file.
- 10: (IDRS_NODICTFILE), Cannot find dictionary file.
- 11: (IDRS_BADLU), Bad logical unit number.
- 12: (IDRS_BADTYPE), Data length or data type illegal.
- 13: (IDRS_AMBIGUITYEXISTS), An ambiguity exists between user vdb and file data.
- 14: (IDRS_CANNOTADDDATA), Cannot add to existing data.
- 15: (IDRS_DICTFULL), Dictionary is full.
- 1016: (IDRS_VERSION1FILE), Warning: version 1 file found.

- 1017: (IDRS_NEWFILEFORMAT), Warning: File format is newer than code.
- 18: (IDRS_CANNOTREADHEADER), Cannot read dictionary file header.
- 19: (IDRS_CANNOTREADDATA), Cannot read data file.
- 20: (IDRS_BADDIMNAME), Bad dimension name.
- 21: (IDRS_TOOMANYFILES), Too many files open.
- 22: (IDRS_CANNOTOPENDICT), Cannot open dictionary file.
- 23: (IDRS_CANNOTOPENDATA), Cannot open data file.
- 24: (IDRS_BADSTATUS), Bad file status specified.
- 25: (IDRS_BADDIMTYPE), Bad dimension type specified.
- 2026: (IDRS_INDEXHIGH), Lookup found index larger than vector length.
- 2027: (IDRS_INDEXLOW), Lookup returned 0 index.
- 2028: (IDRS_INDEXBETWEEN), Element is in vector range, but does not match a vector value.
- 29: (IDRS_NORANGE), A data range does not overlap file data.
- 30: (IDRS_SAVEBUFOVERFLOW), Internal save buffer overflow
- 31: (IDRS_BADERRLEVEL), A bad error report level was specified
- 32: (IDRS_ERROROUTOFRANGE), Error number is out of range.
- 33: (IDRS_CANNOTWRITEHEADER), Cannot write dictionary file header
- 34: (IDRS_CANNOTWRITEDATA), Cannot write a data file record.
- 35: (IDRS_BADCHARLEN), A Cray variable character length is not a multiple of 8.
- 36: (IDRS_BADOPER), A bad dictionary file inquiry operator was specified.
- 1037: (IDRS_NOMOREVARS), Warning: No more matching variables found in search.
- 38: (IDRS_DICTALREADYOPEN), Dictionary file is already open on a different unit.

- 2039: (IDRS_LOOKUPFAILED), Dictionary lookup failed.
- 40: (IDRS_DICTWRITEERROR, Error writing to dictionary file.
- 41: (IDRS_DICTEXTENDERROR), Error extending dictionary file.
- 42: (IDRS_DATAEXTENDERROR), Error extending data file.
- 43: (IDRS_DICTRUNCATEERR), Error truncating dictionary file.
- 44: (IDRS_DATAATTRUNCATEERR), Error truncating data file.
- 1045: (IDRS_BADIEEEFP), Bad IEEE floating-point number, cannot translate.
- 1046: (IDRS_BADCRAYFP), Bad CRAY floating-point number, cannot translate.
- 1047: (IDRS_BADCRAYINT), Bad CRAY integer encountered during translation.
- 48: (IDRS_CANNOTCONVERT), Cannot convert data as requested.
- 1049 (IDRS_INEXACTMATCH, Naming info is similar, but names do not match.

A.2

DRS Errors by Name

- IDRS_AMBIGUITYEXISTS=13, An ambiguity exists between user vdb and file data.
- IDRS_BADCHARLEN=35, A Cray variable character length is not a multiple of 8.
- IDRS_BADCRAYFP=1046, Bad CRAY floating-point number, cannot translate.
- IDRS_BADCRAYINT=1047, Bad CRAY integer encountered during translation.
- IDRS_BADDIM=7, An input dimension is incorrect.
- IDRS_BADDIMNAME=20, Bad dimension name.
- IDRS_BADDIMTYPE=25, Bad dimension type specified.
- IDRS_BADERRLEVEL=31, A bad error report level was specified.
- IDRS_BADIEEEFP=1045, Bad IEEE floating-point number, cannot translate.
- IDRS_BADLEN=3, vector length was .lt.1 or not large enough for actual data.
- IDRS_BADLU=11, Bad logical unit number.
- IDRS_BADOPER=36, A bad dictionary file inquiry operator was specified.
- IDRS_BADSTATUS=24, Bad file status specified.
- IDRS_BADTYPE=12, Data length or data type illegal.
- IDRS_BINFAILED=2002, Data value lookup failed.
- IDRS_CANNOTADDDATA=14, Cannot add to existing data.
- IDRS_CANNOTCONVERT=48, Cannot convert data as requested.

- IDRS_CANNOTOPENDATA=23, Cannot open data file.
- IDRS_CANNOTOPENDICT=22, Cannot open dictionary file.
- IDRS_CANNOTREADDATA=19, Cannot read data file.
- IDRS_CANNOTREADHEADER=18, Cannot read dictionary file header.
- IDRS_CANNOTWRITEDATA=34, Cannot write a data file record.
- IDRS_CANNOTWRITEHEADER=33, Cannot write dictionary file header.
- IDRS_DATEXTENDERROR=42, Error extending data file.
- IDRS_DATTRUNCATEERR=44, Error truncating data file.
- IDRS_DICTALREADYOPEN=38, Dictionary file is already open on a different unit.
- IDRS_DICTEXTENDERROR=41, Error extending dictionary file.
- IDRS_DICTFULL=15, Dictionary is full.
- IDRS_DICTREADERROR=9, Error reading dictionary file.
- IDRS_DICTTRUNCATEERR=43, Error truncating dictionary file.
- IDRS_DICTWRITEERROR=40, Error writing to dictionary file.
- IDRS_ERROROUTOFRANGE=32, Error number is out of range.
- IDRS_INDEXBETWEEN=2028, Element is in vector range, but does not match a vector value.
- IDRS_INDEXHIGH=2026, Lookup found index larger than vector length.
- IDRS_INDEXLOW=2027, Lookup returned 0 index.
- IDRS_INEXACTMATCH=1049, Naming info is similar, but names do not match.
- IDRS_LOOKUPFAILED=2039, Dictionary lookup failed.
- IDRS_NEWFILEFORMAT=1017, Warning: File format is newer than code.
- IDRS_NOCOMPARISON=5, Variable names do not compare.
- IDRS_NODICTFILE=10, Cannot find dictionary file.
- IDRS_NOMEMORY=1, Cannot allocate dynamic memory.
- IDRS_NOMONO=4, No monotonicity specified for a search vector of length greater than 1.
- IDRS_NOMOREVARS=1037, Warning: No more matching variables found in search.
- IDRS_NORANGE=29, A data range does not overlap file data.
- IDRS_NOTMONOTONE=8, Resulting dimension variable will not be monotone.
- IDRS_SAVEBUFOVERFLOW=30, Internal save buffer overflow.
- IDRS_SUCCESS=0, The function completed successfully.
- IDRS_TOOMANYFILES=21, Too many files open.
- IDRS_VDBNOTFOUND=6, Variable not found in dictionary.
- IDRS_VERSION1FILE=1016, Warning: version 1 file found.

PCMDI REPORTS

<u>Number</u>	<u>Title</u>	<u>Authors(s)</u>	<u>Date</u>
1	The Validation of Atmospheric Model	W. L. Gates	March 1992
2	Analysis of the Temporal Behavior of Tropical Convection in the ECMWF Model	J. M. Slingo K. R. Sperber J.-J. Morcrette G. L. Potter	April 1992
3	The Effect of Horizontal Resolution on Ocean Surface Heat Fluxes in the ECMWF Model	P. J. Gleckler K. E. Taylor	July 1992
4	Behavior of an Ocean General Circulation Model at Four Different Horizontal Resolutions	C. Covey	August 1992
5	The Effects of Sampling Frequency on the Climate Statistics of the ECMWF General Circulation Model	T. J. Phillips W. L. Gates K. Arpe	September 1992
6	Sensitivity of Dynamical Quantities to Horizontal Resolution in a Climate Simulation with the ECMWF Atmospheric General Circulation Model (Cycle 33)	J. S. Boyle	October 1992
7	AMIP: The Atmospheric Model Intercomparison Project	W. L. Gates	December 1992
8	The Impact of Horizontal Resolution on Moist Processes in the ECMWF Model	T. J. Phillips L. C. Corsetti S. L. Grotch	January 1993

<u>Number</u>	<u>Title</u>	<u>Authors(s)</u>	<u>Date</u>
9	A Modeling Perspective on Cloud Radiative Forcing	G. L. Potter J. M. Slingo J.-J. Morcrette L. Corsetti	February 1993
10	The Use of General Circulation Models in Detecting Climate Change Induced By Greenhouse Gases	B. D. Santer U. Cubasch U. Mikolajewicz G. Hegerl	March 1993
11	Preliminary Validation of the Low Frequency Variability of Tropospheric Temperature and Circulation Simulated for the AMIP by the ECMWF Model	J. S. Boyle	April 1993

